

Selected topic: GENOME AND METAGENOME ANALYSIS

Metagenomic Insights into Soil Microbiomes of Natural and Semi-Natural Habitats in Vojvodina: Implication for Carbon Sequestration and Nature-based Solutions

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In a world facing global challenges such as climate change and soil degradation, understanding the role of the soil microbiome in carbon sequestration is essential for developing sustainable land-use strategies and preserving ecosystem services. This PhD research focuses on metagenomic analysis of soil microbiomes from natural and semi-natural habitats in Vojvodina (Serbia). The main objective is to investigate the taxonomic and functional diversity of microbial communities and their potential role in carbon sequestration. Special emphasis is placed on identifying microbial groups involved in the transformation of organic matter and the stabilization of organic carbon in soil. A total of 200 soil samples were collected during the spring/summer seasons in 2024 and 2025, and the ongoing analysis integrates shotgun sequencing data with physico-chemical soil properties to uncover relevant correlations. The expected outcomes will support soil health assessment and reveal opportunities for implementing Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in Vojvodina, with the overarching aim of conserving soil biodiversity and mitigating climate change. These findings will also inform regional land-use policies and foster stakeholder engagement in adopting NbS for enhanced climate resilience and sustainable soil management.

KEYWORDS: soil microbiome; metagenomics; carbon sequestration, nature-based solutions

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